

THE MAIN FEATURES OF PEDAGOGICAL STRATEGIES ON IMPROVING THE QUALITY OF EDUCATION IN PRESIDENTIAL SCHOOLS IN UZBEKISTAN

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Abstract. *This article deals with pedagogical strategies for improving the quality of education in the Presidential schools such as vision and mission of Presidential schools and high quality of learning and teaching (HQLT); their impact on the educational process of students, consistent monitoring and management of the educational process in the Presidential schools during educational process.*

Keywords: *sustainability, global society, UN Convention of the Rights of the Child (1990), high quality of learning and teaching (HQLT)*

As we notice that these days around the globe, special attention is being given to the importance of innovative pedagogical strategies which is being more and more essential for preparing globally competent and intellectually developed specialists to our society. When we look at the vision and mission of Presidential schools we can easily notice that there very special approach is represented as a key factor. Here are given extracts from the Constitution of Presidential schools of Uzbekistan below:

1.0 Philosophy

The Presidential Schools program represents transformative education for the Republic of Uzbekistan and an investment in the future of the country through the development of its most promising youth. The aim of the program is to develop leaders who are competitive in the world market, and can serve their country in the areas of science, economics, politics, technology and sustainability.

1.1 Vision

The vision of the Presidential Schools is to prepare the next generation of leaders to actively and positively contribute to the development of Uzbekistan by providing educational opportunities that encourage the nation's gifted and talented youth to realize their potential as creative, innovative participants in a dynamic global society.

1.2 Mission

The mission of the Presidential Schools (PS) is to enhance the educational experience for gifted students through a programme of academic excellence and holistic learning opportunities to develop the leadership potential of its graduates to contribute to the future of Uzbekistan.

1.3 Profile of a Presidential School graduate

The profile of a Presidential School graduate identifies the attributes of a student able to successfully meet the challenges of the program's vision and mission. The attributes serve as a clear visualization of the ultimate goals of learning and teaching.

- Ethical citizen
 - I demonstrate my civic responsibility to the Republic of Uzbekistan and to the global community through my positive contributions to society and my ethical decision- making;

- Critical thinker
 - I use reliable and relevant evidence to develop understanding across a broad range of disciplines to design and implement solutions to complex problems;
- Responsible
 - I take responsibility for my own actions and the consequences that accompany them, and view risk as an opportunity to learn;
- Academically prepared
 - I demonstrate mastery of academic skills and diligently pursue self-improvement in my understanding through achievements in coursework, competitions and research;
- Leader
 - I lead others by setting direction and creating a shared vision, by showing empathy and the willingness to consider different perspectives;
- Global citizen
 - I understand and appreciate my own culture and personal histories, and have respect for others' perspectives, values and attitudes. I acknowledge my duty as a global citizen to advocate for the sustainable development and environmental stewardship of my country and the world;
- Collaborator
 - I understand and express ideas and information confidently and creatively and through a variety of modes of communication. I seek a diversity of perspectives and value individual contributions toward problem-solving;
- Balanced
 - I develop myself in mind, body and spirit and understand the importance of emotional balance to achieve my personal well-being and that of others.

1.4 Ethics and Responsibility

The Presidential Schools (PS) network envisions a vibrant learning community with a shared vision and mission in which all stakeholders contribute to building a healthy and respectful environment where rights are respected, and all members find support and encouragement. This vision is supported by a shared code of ethics about wellness, respect, transparency and fidelity that provides guidance in decision making and interactions between community members.

- Wellness

Wellness of students and staff is the foundation of a healthy community, and is the primary consideration in all matters. All decisions and interactions of the Presidential Schools are to be measured against this statement. The Presidential Schools aligns its practices with the UN Convention of the Rights of the Child (1990), of which the Republic of Uzbekistan is a signatory. Among all rights, PS specifically acknowledges the right to equitable education, the right to academic, social and emotional development, the right to develop as an individual, the rights of the parents in supporting the child, and the right of a child to relax and play.

- Respect

All members of the community are treated with respect. The Presidential Schools network does not tolerate any form of discrimination or behavior in which stakeholders are deprived of their right to respectful and dignified exchange.

- Transparency

All operations and decisions made by agents and employees of the Presidential Schools are executed with policy guidance and the transparency necessary to ensure fair, legal and procedurally driven actions. This statement is reinforced through a Complaints and Appeals Policy with a clear procedure and remedies accessible to all stakeholders.

- Fidelity

All stakeholders commit to understand, respect and work toward the shared vision and mission of the Presidential Schools, and in the best interests of the students who the community serves. Policies and practices are developed for the welfare and positive development of the students in the care of the school, and in pursuit of the aspirational goals of the Presidential Schools network.

As we see above, the main document of Presidential schools in Uzbekistan is based on preparing the next generation of leaders who actively and positively contribute to the development of Uzbekistan by providing educational opportunities that encourage the nation's gifted and talented youth to realize their potential as creative, innovative participants in a dynamic global society by being global citizens. At the same time, we must keep in mind the role of high quality of learning and teaching (HQLT) in educational process of the schools.

Definition of HQLT

High quality learning and teaching is the development of individuals into responsible future leaders equipped with high levels of knowledge, skills and values, incorporating a student-centered learning approach, catering for the learners' personal and cultural well-being to make a positive impact in a globalized world.

Figure-1. Overall vision of Visible thinking and learning.

Since student-centered learning is one of the main features of HQLT, the role of it is important educational process. Let's see how to create student-centered classes. After understanding all of the high-level benefits of student-centered learning, how do you actually create SCL classes? First, we have to get input from students themselves. We built this student self-assessment tool during hybrid learning, and it continues to support conversations with students around educational goals. You can use it to make sure any changes you make support key design principles like caring, trusting relationships, meaningful, engaged learning, and youth voice and choice.

Once you've gathered input from students and other stakeholders, a sequential list of some of the most critical steps to take to implement SCL includes:

- Giving students introductory autonomous assignments and helping them set their goals for those assignments

- Helping students become acquainted with their preferred ways of learning new material
- Becoming more responsive to students' areas of interest and passion
- Gradually increasing the amount of control students have to set their assignments and learning agendas
 - Having teachers shift from a leading role to a facilitating and resource role for student-selected activities
 - Creating a physical (or virtual) class layout that makes it easy for students to collaborate
 - Asking students to start gauging their learning accomplishments rather than relying solely on the results of standardized tests.

For examples of SCL projects and lesson ideas, so let's explore:

- How students at Brooklyn Lab applied rhetoric and communication skills to issues they care about through a TEDx event
- How students at New Harmony explored climate change through storytelling
- The projects students at Crosstown High built around the question "Should we go to Mars and should we change it?"
- Círculos's 9th grade Ash + Feather arts residency
- Purdue Polytechnic students building EV Carts

Figure-2. Student -centered learning techniques by Cambridge Assessment.

Nowadays both our government and ministry under the leadership of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, Shavkat Mirziyoyev have been giving more attention than ever to the role of education process in schools and our President emphasized those approaches in his books, speeches and live meetings with scientists. After all, the ideas and teachings of scholars such as

Bukhari and Termizi, Farabi and Ferghani, Ibn Sina and Al-Khwarizmi, Ulugbek and Navoi, who were born and raised in the territory of our country on the basis of the specific values of our culture formed in our republic, universal human principles, scientific and theoretical aimed at the spiritual positive development of young people's views and the fact that our country has passed a new stage of development and its contributions to the entire world civilization are incomparable. As a proof of this, the research of this scientific and cultural heritage, scientific research, in turn, is reflected in the works of our President. On the date August 28 of 2023 year there was held a live video, meeting of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Sh. Mirziyoyev on "Priority tasks for further improving the quality of education in schools, increasing the number of students and improving the qualifications of teachers and creating suitable conditions for them". Our president paid a special attention to education system of pre-school and school education with his highly motivational and critical speech on school educational innovations.

Finally, as we work to create lessons that meet the personalized needs of students, it's crucial to keep in mind how each student's experience and capacity at school is impacted by their individual circumstances. Understanding—and having empathy for—every student is crucial to building a learning plan that works for them. To that end, Brooklyn Lab created a tool during the pandemic period in 2000 to help educators does just that: Student Personas for Empathy-Building. This interactive method focuses on five student personas, along with the counselors, teachers, and other adults who support them. Educators can explore each persona to see how that student's school experience is impacted by other life circumstances—and in doing so; consider what accommodations to lessons could help those students succeed. To sum up, using the innovative pedagogical strategies on improving the quality of education in Presidential schools in Uzbekistan is on the developing stage and needs more practice as time goes by. At the same time, during the observation process of the school, we encountered the tendency of SCL in classes performing by international teachers as mostly approved and appreciated by the students. The observation indicates that, innovative pedagogical strategies such as HQLT and SCL are widely used educational process of the schools which helps students to reach their goals as well as performing the mission and vision of the school that they have targeted to accomplish.

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